

Spectrophotometric Studies on Cobalt(II) with Maleonitrile Dithiolate

S. P. BAG* and B. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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The analytical application of maleonitrile dithiolate for liquid-liquid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt is reported. The brown complex absorbs maximum at 460 nm. The system obeys Beer's law from 1.0 to 8.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 5.01×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.01 µg of Co²⁺/cm² respectively. The metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 2. Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, Pd²⁺ and Pt⁴⁺ interfere in the determination. The stability constants (log k_1 and k_2) are 4.15 and 3.55 at 25 ± 1°.

COBALT forms intensely coloured complexes with heterocyclic azodyes¹. Dyes with PAN-type chelating agent act as tridentate ligand. The other important reagents for cobalt are α-nitroso-β-naphthol², nitroso-R salt³, salicylaldehyde⁴, 2,3-quinoxaline dithiol⁵, picolinaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone⁶ and 6-nitroquinoxaline 2,3-dithiol⁷.

In the present investigation the applicability of maleonitrile dithiolate for liquid-liquid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt has been studied. The stepwise formation constants, k_1 and k_2 of the complexes CoL₁⁺ and CoL₂, respectively have been evaluated following the graphical extrapolation method of Leden⁸ and Yatsimirskii⁹⁻¹¹. The overall formation constant has also been evaluated by Harvey-Mannings¹² method.

Experimental

Equipment :

A Higher Uvispek spectrophotometer and Spectromom 204, with 1 cm quartz cells were used for measurement for absorbance.

Preparation of solution :

The standard solution of cobalt was prepared by dissolving 0.1 g of spectroscopically pure cobalt (Johnson and Matthey) in hydrochloric acid (AnalaR). After complete dissolution by repeated boiling, the solution was slowly evaporated to expel the free acid. The residue was then extracted with double distilled water and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were taken for preparation of standard curve.

Preparation of reagent :

Maleonitrile dithiolate was prepared by the method of Bahr and Schleitzer¹³ as modified by Davison and Holm¹⁴.

Finely powdered sodium cyanide (29.49 g) and dimethyl formamide (180 ml) were placed in a flask. Pure carbon disulphide (36.2 ml) was added into the flask dropwise. The reaction product was dissolved in hot isobutyl alcohol (500 ml) and filtered to remove sodium cyanide. The product was recovered from the filtrate on cooling. The yellow brown solid was recrystallized by dissolving in hot absolute ethanol and reprecipitating with anhydrous ether, yield 27 g. (Found : C, 25.50; H, 0.04; N, 14.75; S, 34.30. Calcd. for N₂C₄Na₂S₂; C, 25.80; H, 0.00; N, 15.05; S, 34.45%). The compound decomposed above 300°.

Freshly prepared 0.1% aqueous solution was used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Results and Discussion

Optimal spectral characteristics :

The absorbance spectra of 4 ppm cobalt complex and reagent in MIBK medium in the wavelength region 400-540 nm show absorption maxima at 460 and 400 nm, respectively (Fig. 1). 0.2 to 1.0 M HCl was found sufficient for full colour development and extraction of the cobalt complex. The optimum acidity range for complex formation was from 0.2 to 0.5 M HCl. The optimum reagent concentration was 4.0 to 8.0 ml of the 0.1% reagent solution. The complex system is stable for at least 1 hr.

Solvent extraction characteristics :

The extraction behaviour of the cobalt complex in aqueous and non-aqueous (MIBK) phase ratio of 1 : 1 have been studied. The acidity was maintained at 0.5 M HCl and 5 ml of 0.1% aqueous solution of reagent was added. It was observed that 99% of the complex was extracted in a single extraction and that 100% extraction was possible in two operations.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 4 ppm of cobalt complex against reagent blank in MIBK medium (B); Absorption spectra of reagent in MIBK medium against solvent blank (A).

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error, molar absorptivity and sensitivity :

The complex system obeyed Beer's law from 1.0 to 8.0 ppm (Fig. 2). The optimum range for determination, as obtained by Ringbom's plot¹⁵, was found to be 2.0 to 8.0 ppm. The percent relative error obtained from Ayres¹⁶ equation for the system is 2.68. The molar absorptivity of Co^{2+} complex calculated from Beer's law is $5.01 \times 10^3 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The sensitivity according to Sandell's definition is $0.01 \mu\text{g of Co}^{2+}/\text{cm}^2$.

Fig. 2. Beer's law curve.

Recommended procedure :

An aliquot of cobalt solution ($100 \mu\text{g}$) is taken into a separatory funnel and the acidity condition is maintained at 0.5 M HCl . 5 ml of 0.1% reagent solution in water is added and the aqueous and non-aqueous (MIBK) ratio is maintained at 1 : 1. The mixture is shaken for 5 min with 15 ml of MIBK. The extraction is repeated with 5 ml of solvent. The combined extract is dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a 50 ml beaker and transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume is made up with pure MIBK. The absorbance of the cobalt complex is measured at 460 nm against reagent blank prepared similarly.

Composition of the complex :

The composition of the brown Co^{2+} complex was determined by the continuous variation¹⁷ and molar ratio¹⁸ methods following the adopted procedures. Equimolar solutions of reagents and Co^{2+} ($6.78 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) were mixed in complimentary mixture of 12 ml volume. The Co^{2+} : reagent ratio was found to be 1 : 2. The composition was verified by mole-ratio method using 1 ml of $1.70 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and a plot of absorbance against increasing ligand concentration gave a break at metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of foreign ions on the determination of 4 ppm of Co^{2+} with the reagent was studied by extracting the complexes in presence of varying amounts of added foreign ions. Tolerance limit for the variation is fixed at 0.005 unit at 460 nm. It has been found that 200 fold excess of Pb^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , V^{4+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , tartrate, citrate, acetate, oxalate, nitrate, sulphate, fluoride, thiocyanate, EDTA is tolerated in the determination. Fe^{3+} can be masked by bifluoride. Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , W^{6+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{4+} interfere. However, palladium can be removed by prior extraction with dimethylglyoxime in chloroform and excess dimethylglyoxime is destroyed by boiling with nitric acid. Cobalt can be quantitatively extracted in presence of copper if iodide and thiosulphate are added. Nickel can be masked by sodium borate and molybdenum can be masked by fluoride.

Fig. 3. Plots of Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 from Leden's method.

Fig. 4. Subsidiary function f_1, f_2 as a function of free ligand concentration.

Fig. 5. ϵ, g as a function of reciprocal of free ligand concentration.

Stability constants :

The degree of dissociation, α , was calculated to be 0.231 from the relation $\alpha = Am - As / Am$. The K (instability constant) value is 1.88×10^{-9} for the 1 : 2 complex at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The Co^{2+} concentration in the Harvey-Manning's equation is 1.70×10^{-3} molar. The stability constant, K, value is found to be 5.32×10^8 and $\log K$ is 8.73.

The $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ evaluated by considering the degree of complex formation function (ϕ) and graphical extrapolation method of Leden are 4.15 and 3.55. The value of $\log K$ is 7.70 (Fig 3).

The stepwise formation constants were further verified by Yatsimirskii's method considering the different functions f_1, f_2, ϵ and g . The $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ are found to be 4.36 and 4.18, respectively. The value of $\log K$ is 8.55 (Fig. 4 and 5).

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